

ANALYSIS OF STRUCTURAL CHANGES IN BASIC AND SPECIFIC MOTOR ABILITIES AMONG FEMALE POLICE OFFICER CANDIDATES DURING ONE YEAR OF TRAINING

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Abstract

The primary objective of police training is to enable the acquisition of practical knowledge and skills essential for the successful execution of professional duties. To ensure the quality preparation of future police personnel, it is of particular importance that the methodological concept and structure of the training are aligned with the real demands and needs of the policing profession. Within the Training Centre of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, a contemporary model of police education is implemented, focused on developing the key activities and competencies required for the performance of police tasks. In this study, a specific methodological procedure was applied to assess the feedback effects of one year of police training on the basic and specific motor abilities of 72 female police officer candidates aged 20 to 25. The assessment of general and specific motor preparedness was conducted during the first, second, and third training modules, using a standardized battery of motor tests and tests measuring competencies in defensive techniques. The results of the statistical analysis indicate that during the one-year training, positive changes occurred in most of the basic and specific motor abilities of the female police candidates. However, it was found that these changes did not reach the expected quality level according to the evaluation scoring scale. Based on these findings, the need for revision and correction of certain parts of the training curriculum is highlighted, with the aim of enabling a higher degree of professional transformation and the development of police personnel capable of responding to contemporary security challenges and professional demands.

Keywords: *police education, police officer candidates, statistical analysis, motor preparedness*

INTRODUCTION

The policing profession ranks among those that require a high level of both physical and psychological preparedness due to the nature of the tasks performed by police officers and their constant exposure to risk and stress. Police officers are expected to maintain optimal physical fitness not only as a prerequisite for successfully performing their duties but also as an indicator of professionalism, self-discipline, and readiness to protect public safety and citizens (Anderson et al., 2001).

Maintaining physical fitness is a fundamental element of police service, as it enables the effective and efficient execution of operational tasks, improvement of health and well-being, development of discipline and endurance, and the promotion of teamwork and communication within police structures (Ивановски, Јаневски & Недев, 2010).

Law enforcement is a physically demanding, psychologically challenging, and potentially dangerous profession that often carries significant health implications for officers. Police officers face daily tasks that require physical endurance – such as running, overcoming resistance, restraining offenders, applying coercive measures, and carrying equipment and weapons (Anderson & Plecas, 2000). At the same time, they are exposed to high levels of social and psychological pressure arising from the nature of police work, the need for quick and accurate decision-making, and dealing with risky and stressful situations.

Physically demanding occupations, such as policing, require high levels of cardiovascular fitness, muscular strength, and endurance. Consequently, educational institutions responsible for the selection and training of candidates establish physical fitness standards that must be met for entry into police academies (Payne & Harvey 2010). Within modern educational and training systems, physical training represents an integral part of police education and professional development (Klisarič, 2003). Modern police education and training programs include curricula aimed at developing specific competencies, psychophysical abilities, and personal qualities required for effective policing (Lagestad & Tillaar, 2014).

This modern training approach enhances the ability for self-reflection, critical thinking, and decision-making in high-risk situations – skills that are essential for the contemporary police officer (Merry & Grimshaw, 2019). Therefore, physical preparedness should not be perceived solely as a biological or athletic category but rather as an integral component of the police officer's professional identity and a fundamental prerequisite for the successful implementation of policing tasks in the service of public safety and the rule of law.

ORGANIZATION AND METHODOLOGY OF CONDUCTING BASIC POLICE TRAINING

Basic police training represents a fundamental component within the system of police education and serves the purpose of ensuring the continuous replenishment of personnel within the Ministry of Internal Affairs. The recruitment of police candidates is conducted through a public announcement, followed by a structured selection procedure (Training Rulebook of the Ministry of Interior, 2009, Article 92). This selection process unfolds through several consecutive phases aimed at identifying candidates who possess the necessary psychophysical, intellectual, and moral qualities. Candidates who successfully pass the selection procedure are referred to a one-year training program at the Training Centre in Idrizovo.

The contemporary concept of the Basic Police Training Program at the Training Centre is grounded in the principles of European police education systems and introduces new dimensions in the approach to police education (Nikač et al., 2011). The program is implemented through a blended learning model that combines activities conducted within the educational institution and practical work in operational police units. Such a model establishes a balance between theoretical knowledge and practical skills, thereby ensuring

effective preparation of future police officers for the competent, lawful, and professional performance of their duties (Trajkov, 2012).

In designing the curriculum for basic police training, the following aspects were taken into consideration:

- Analysis of police job tasks to determine the key competencies required of police candidates;
- The national legislative framework;
- International standards and recommendations in the field of police education;
- The specific needs of the police and the community.

The primary goal of the program is to provide a systematic approach to developing the professional and practical competencies of future police officers. Accordingly, the training is designed to meet the following priority objectives:

- Advancement of professional competencies, including the understanding of laws, procedures, and techniques essential for performing basic police duties;
- Development of practical skills for effective action in diverse field situations;
- Improvement of communication and interpersonal skills to foster trust and effective cooperation with the community.

The curriculum for basic police training is structured around four key components:

1. Core Activities and Competencies. This component defines the essential tasks and competencies that candidates are expected to acquire during training, closely aligned with the operational realities of police work. It ensures the harmonization of acquired knowledge and skills with the needs of police practice, fostering the development of professional attitudes and values.

2. Competency Assessment Tests. This component serves to evaluate the level of knowledge, skills, and behaviour acquired by candidates throughout the training process. Continuous monitoring and assessment provide a realistic picture of the candidates' professional preparedness and competency levels.

3. Learning Environments. The training is carried out across two interrelated learning environments: formal (within the Training Centre) and non-formal (in police organizational units). Over the one-year cycle, candidates spend nine months at the Training Centre and three months in the field, applying their acquired knowledge in a real-world environment. This model enables gradual educational and professional transformation, strengthening the link between theory and practice.

4. Quality Assurance System. This component establishes mechanisms for continuous monitoring and evaluation of the educational process. The feedback system allows for performance analysis, assessment of outcomes, and planning for the enhancement of future training programs through curriculum review and improvement.

In line with the established implementation dynamics of these key components, the basic police training is conducted over a twelve-month period through a dual learning system that integrates theoretical and practical aspects of police education. The training includes a nine-month theoretical phase at the Training Centre, consisting of 1,134 hours of instruction with trainers and 415 hours of self-study, followed by a three-month field practicum in police stations under the supervision of field mentors, comprising a total of 378 hours (Curriculum for basic police training, Ministry of Interior, 2013).

The alternating cycle of theoretical and practical activities enables a balanced distribution of responsibilities inherent to the specific nature of police training. This approach ensures continuity between the theoretical study of essential instructional

elements and their practical application in a real professional setting, providing the foundation for the development of applicable knowledge, skills, and competencies.

To ensure a high standard of training quality, the curriculum is organized into three thematic modules (Basic training on human rights in police operations, 2014):

Module 1: Fundamentals of Police Work and Public Order Protection

Module 2: Protection of Life and Property

Module 3: General Jurisdiction, Road Traffic Safety, and Border Operations.

The first module constitutes the foundational phase in developing the professional knowledge and competencies of future police officers. It encompasses essential activities and tasks based on respect for human rights and freedoms, and the principles of lawful, proportional, and responsible exercise of police authority.

The second module focuses on the acquisition of practical knowledge and skills relevant to everyday operational police activities. Its content includes topics such as arrest and detention of individuals, scene security, and the undertaking of appropriate measures and actions in cases involving offenses against public order, illicit drug trafficking, illegal possession of firearms, and other security threats.

The third module develops specialized knowledge and competencies required for the regulation and supervision of road traffic safety and border operations. Special emphasis is placed on issues of border control, combating cross-border crime, preventing illegal migration, and strengthening cross-border police cooperation.

Evaluation of training outcomes is carried out through knowledge and competency tests, designed to objectively assess the level of mastery of theoretical content and practical skills. Each test contains a detailed description of tasks and a list of criteria (competencies) that candidates must meet to demonstrate readiness for performing police duties in real professional contexts.

Within the framework of the basic police training program, a distinct component focuses on the education and training aimed at improving the general and specific motor preparedness of police candidates (Ivanovski, 2020). The objective of physical training is the planned and systematic development of fundamental motor abilities and the acquisition of specific knowledge and skills required for the lawful and effective use of coercive measures in various security situations.

Given the complexity of the curriculum structure and the necessity to shape an appropriate professional profile of future police officers, the allocated number of hours for general physical preparation amounts to (48+20) hours, while the instruction dedicated to learning and mastering defensive techniques comprises (82+16) hours.

The content of the general physical training includes diverse activities aimed at enhancing aerobic and anaerobic endurance, strength, flexibility (active and passive), agility, coordination, balance, the ability to overcome spatial and artificial obstacles (obstacle courses), training with equipment and weights, and running over various distances (cross-country, sprint, etc.).

Specific physical training focuses on the systematic acquisition and improvement of defensive techniques and practical police procedures related to the lawful use of force and police powers. The program covers police stance and combat posture, movements in combat position, strikes and defences using arms and legs, falling and throwing techniques, control techniques for overcoming passive and active resistance, defence techniques against armed and unarmed attackers, and techniques for the use of police batons and restraining devices.

The instructional process employs a variety of teaching methods, including verbal explanation, demonstration, practical exercise, corrective training, circuit training, self-learning, and scenario simulation (role-playing).

Beyond methodological aspects, the organization of instruction incorporates additional measures aimed at maintaining order and discipline, ensuring compliance with health and hygiene standards, providing adequate assistance during exercises, and securing the necessary material and technical conditions. The purpose of these measures is to enhance the quality, safety, and efficiency of the physical training process as an essential component of the professional development of future police officers.

SUBJECT AND OBJECTIVE OF THE RESEARCH

The subject of this research is the general and specific motor abilities of female candidates for police officers, measured throughout a one-year training course at the Training Centre of the Ministry of the Interior.

The objective of the study is to determine the changes and transformations occurring among the trainees in their general and specific motor abilities under the influence of the physical training program, as well as to assess the extent to which the established standards and evaluation criteria meet educational and professional requirements.

RESEARCH METHOD

Sample of respondents

The research sample consists of 72 female candidates for police officers, aged between 20 and 25 years. During the one-year training course, three testing sessions were conducted after completing the instruction for the first, second, and third modules. The tests were administered at four-month intervals in the gymnasium and at the stadium of the Training Centre by instructors responsible for the implementation of the physical training program.

Sample of variables

To evaluate the general and specific motor preparedness of the candidates, two categories of tests were applied:

1. Tests for assessing general physical preparedness:
 - 60-meter agility run (R60m)
 - Standing long jump (JUMP)
 - Sit-ups in 30 seconds (ABS30)
 - Push-ups (PUSH UP)
 - 1000-meter run (R1000m)
2. Tests for assessing specific physical preparedness:
 - Hand and elbow striking techniques
 - Kicking and knee striking techniques
 - Defensive techniques against hand strikes
 - Defensive techniques against leg strikes
 - Identification stance techniques
 - Control and restraint techniques – arrest procedures

- Falling techniques
- Throwing techniques
- Defence techniques against unarmed attacker
- Defence techniques against armed attacker
- Handcuffing techniques
- Use of the police baton

In accordance with the physical training program, for each module, separate tests of general and specific motor preparedness were conducted using point-based evaluation scales. The overall score obtained from all tests was used to assess the level of physical preparedness of each candidate throughout the training process.

Statistical methods for data processing

To obtain feedback on the general and specific physical preparedness of the candidates during the research period, descriptive statistical procedures were employed. For each measurement, the mean values (\bar{X}) were calculated, and statistically significant differences between the three measurements were determined using the T-test. Additionally, a classification method – frequency analysis (f%) – was applied to determine the distribution of results across score categories.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF THE RESULTS OF THE RESEARCH

Table 1 presents the criteria for evaluating motor abilities among the female police officer candidates, ranging from 1 to 14 points. These scoring criteria enable an objective assessment of the candidates’ motor abilities and allow for the monitoring of both individual and group progress throughout the training process.

Table 1. Criteria for assessing the motor abilities of the respondents

R60m	JUMP	ABS30	PUSH UP	R1000m
Up to	155-160.....1	13.....1	12.....1	Up to 4.40.....14
16.5.....14	161-165.....2	14.....2	13.....2	4.41-4.45.....13
16.6-16.8.....13	166-170.....3	15.....3	14.....3	4.46-4.50.....12
16.9-17.1.....12	171-175.....4	16.....4	15.....4	4.51-4.55.....11
17.2-17.4.....11	176-180.....5	17.....5	16.....5	4.56-5.00.....10
17.5-17.7.....10	181-185.....6	18.....6	17.....6	5.01-5.05.....9
17.8-18.0.....9	186-190.....7	19.....7	18.....7	5.06-5.10.....8
18.1-18.3.....8	191-195.....8	20.....8	19.....8	5.11-5.15.....7
18.4-18.6.....7	196-200.....9	21.....9	20.....9	5.16-5.20.....6
18.7-18.9.....6	201-205.....10	22.....10	21.....10	5.21-5.25.....5
19.0-19.2.....5	206-210.....11	23.....11	22.....11	5.26-5.30.....4
19.3-19.5.....4	211-215.....12	24.....12	23.....12	5.31-5.35.....3
19.6-19.8.....3	216-220.....13	25.....13	24.....13	5.36-5.40.....2
19.9-20.1.....2	221 +.....14	26 +.....14	25 +.....14	5.41-5.45.....1
20.2-20.4.....1				

Table 2 presents the average values obtained in the motor tests during the first, second, and third training modules. An analysis of the data reveals that there are no significant differences in the mean values between the tests, indicating that the observed changes in the candidates’ motor abilities are less pronounced and do not follow the expected temporal dynamics of the training process.

Table 2. Average values in motor tests of the respondents

Variable	R60m	JUMP	ABS30	PUSH UP	R1000m
Modules	X	X	X	X	X
Module I	18.71	177.31	24.29	24.52	4.70
Module II	23.52	179.89	24.24	23.38	4.69
Module III	17.57	177.22	23.76	22.85	4.35

Table 3 shows the results of the applied t-test assessing the significance of differences in mean values. From the analysis of these results, it can be observed that differences exist between the measurements, however, they are statistically significant only in the following tests: R60m ($t = 2.38$, Modules I–III), Push-up ($t = 3.44$, Modules I–III), and R1000m ($t = 1.98$, Modules I–III). These statistical findings indicate that only minor changes have occurred in the motor abilities of the female police cadets during the course of training. Consequently, the objectives of the physical training program were not fully achieved, meaning that the intended educational effect has not been entirely realized.

Table 3. T-test of the applied motor tests between the measurements

R60m	(1)	(2)	(3)	Jump	(1)	(2)	(3)	Ab s 30	(1)	(2)	(3)
	18. 71	23. 52	17. 57		177.3 1	179. 89	177. 22		24. 29	24. 24	23. 76
	(1)				(1)				(1)		
	(2)	- 1.4 3			(2)	- 0.82			(2)	0.1 3	
(3)	2.3 8	1.7 9		(3)	-0.56	0.07	(3)	0.8 9	0.8 1		
Push up	(1)	(2)	(3)	R1000 m	(1)	(2)	(3)				
	24.5 2	23.38	22.8 5		4.70	4.69	4.35				
	(1)				(1)						
	(2)	2.58			(2)	0.05					
(3)	3.44	1.0 2		(3)	1.98	0.88					

Table 4 presents the scoring scale used for assessing the general physical preparedness of the participants during the training, ranging from very low to high levels of physical fitness. Based on the percentage distribution of the results across the scoring categories, it can be observed that there are no major differences in the level of physical preparedness among participants across the three training modules. This implies that, for the most part, the level of physical fitness remained unchanged. According to the distribution of results, the majority of participants demonstrate a medium to high level of physical preparedness, while a smaller number exhibit low or very low levels.

Table 4. Scoring scale for assessing the general physical fitness of the respondents

Points category	N= 72 Module I (f%)	N=72 Module II (f%)	N=72 Module III (f%)	Physical fitness level
< 14	2 (2.77%)	5 (6.94%)	4 (%)	Very low level
15 – 24	7 (9.72%)	3 (4.16%)	6 (8.33%)	Low level
25 - 34	6 (8.33%)	8 (11.11%)	7 (9.72%)	
35 - 44	9 (12.50%)	12 (16.66%)	10 (13.82%)	Moderate level
45 - 54	25 (34.72%)	17 (23.61%)	20 (27.77%)	
55 - 64	16 (22.22%)	19 (26.38%)	17 (23.61%)	High level
65 - 70	7 (9.72%)	8 (11.11%)	8 (11.11%)	

Based on the average values per module presented in Table 5, the group's final score is 46.44 points, which corresponds to a moderate level of general physical preparedness.

Table 5. Average assessment of general physical preparedness among respondents

Average score per module	Final score in training
Module I – 47.86 points	Moderate level of general physical preparedness – 46.44 points
Module II – 45.93 points	
Module III – 45.55 points	

Table 6 presents the scoring scale for assessing the participants' specific physical preparedness during training, ranging from very low to very high. Based on the percentage distribution of results, it is evident that the level of mastery of defensive techniques varies considerably among modules, indicating that the training effects are expressed differently across participants.

Table 6. Scoring scale for assessing specific physical fitness among respondents

Points category	N= 72 Module I (f%)	N=72 Module II (f%)	N=72 Module III (f%)	Level of mastery of defensive techniques
< 4 points	9 (12.50%)	4 (5.55%)	10 (13.88%)	Very low level
5 – 6 points	31 (43.05%)	14 (19.44%)	20 (27.77%)	Low level
7 – 8 points	7 (9.72%)	17 (23.61%)	18 (25.00%)	Moderate level
9 – 10 points	22 (30.55%)	28 (38.88%)	21 (29.16%)	High level
11 – 12 points	3 (4.16%)	9 (12.50%)	3 (4.16%)	Very high level

According to the overall average of acquired knowledge from the defensive techniques training, the group's final score is 7.28 points, which classifies as a moderate level of specific physical preparedness of respondents (Table 7).

Table 7. Average assessment of mastery of defensive techniques among respondents

Average mastery score per module	Overall average mastery score in training
Module I – 8.23 points	Moderate level of knowledge mastery – 7.28 points
Module II – 6.85 points	
Module III – 6.76 points	

The analysis of all indicators obtained from the research demonstrates that female police cadets, to a large extent, successfully complete the physical training and achieve notable progress in both general and specific motor preparedness. Nevertheless, it is necessary to increase the intensity and continuity of the exercises in order to achieve a higher level of applicability of the acquired knowledge and skills in real police practice.

CONCLUSION

Physical training, as an integral component of the basic police education, aims to equip future police officers with the competencies required for safe, lawful, and efficient performance of duties, particularly in the practical application of coercive measures. Considering the numerous prerequisites necessary for developing competent and professional police personnel capable of responding to complex security challenges, it is essential to obtain realistic insights and measurable effects from the implementation of the physical training curriculum.

Based on the conducted analysis and the results obtained from the research, it can be concluded that the tested model of physical training generally produces the desired effects in terms of positive transformation of the general and specific motor abilities of female police cadets throughout the one-year training course. However, these changes do not reach the required level of quality as defined by the scoring assessment scale.

For these reasons, it is necessary to undertake a revision and improvement of the existing physical training program through the introduction of modern training methodologies, an individualized approach to preparation, and an increase in both the intensity and diversity of training activities. Moreover, continuous monitoring and evaluation of the cadets' progress should be implemented to ensure timely adaptation of the teaching process to their physical capabilities and professional needs.

Additionally, investment in improving the material and technical conditions for conducting the training, as well as in the professional development of the teaching staff responsible for physical preparation, is crucial. Such measures would ensure greater efficiency, realism, and applicability of physical training in practical police operations.

REFERENCES

1. Anderson, G. S., Plecas, D., & Segger, T. (2001). Police Officer Physical Ability Testing – Re-validating a Selection Criterion. *Policing: An International Journal*, 24(1), 8-31.
2. Anderson, G. S., & Plecas, D. (2000). Predicting Physical Ability Performance in Police Recruits. *Policing*, 23(1), 8-31.
3. Ivanovski, J. (2020). Influence of the model of physical training on the education of police officer candidates, *Security Horizons, The euro-atlantic values in the balkan countries*, International scientific conference, Faculty of security, Skopje, vol. 1 no. 2, pp.37-49.
4. Ивановски, Ј., Јаневски Т., Недев А. (2010). Вредностите на физичката подготвеност во функција на зголемена безбедност на специјалните полициски цили на МВР, Зборник на трудови од Научно-стручна конференција: Безбедност, еколошка безбедност и предизивиците на Република Македонија, Факултет за безбедност-Скопје, pp. 297-307.
5. Klisarič, M. (2003). Policijska obuka u funkciji zaštite bezbednosti policajaca, *Zbornik radova sa Međunarodno naučno-stručno savetovanje „Ugrožavanje bezbednosti pripadnika policije-uzroci, oblici i mere zaštite“*, Beograd, Policijska akademija, pp. 197-222.
6. Lagestad, P., & van den Tillaar, R. (2014). Longitudinal changes in police officers' physical performance. *Journal of Strength and Conditioning Research*, 28(8), 2366–2374.
7. Merry, S., & Grimshaw, R. (2019). Learning in policing: The value of reflection and experience. *Policing and Society*, 29(3), 241-256.
8. Nikač, Ž., Simic, B., & Blagojević, M. (2011), European model of police training in the function of security police, *International scientific conference security in the post-conflict (western) balkans: transition and challenges faced by the Republic of Macedonia*, Skopje, pp. 34-44.
9. Наставна програма за основна обука за полицаец, Службен весник на Република Македонија, 2014, бр. 42.
10. Основна обука за човекови права при полициско постапување. Министерство за внатрешни работи, Центар за обука (2014), Скопје.
11. Payne, W. R., & Harvey, J. (2010). Physical and psychological preparation for policing. *Police Practice and Research*, 11(1), 37–52.
12. Правилник за обука во МВР, Службен весник на Република Македонија, 120/09, бр. 43/15.
13. Трајков, М. (2012). Современа основна полициска обука во Република Македонија после 2003, Меѓународен годишник, Факултет за безбедност - Скопје, pp.139-149.